

Green synthesis approach of Copper-oxides nanoparticles using leaf extract of *Euphorbia helioscopia* L. for Antibacterial and Antifungal Activity

V. D. Jamnik , Sakshi Ingle, Ashish Vaidya and D. B. Dupare@ *

*@ Department of Chemistry, Shri R.G. Rathod Arts and Science College, Murtizapur, Di. Akola.

Corresponding author Email* : duparedharam5@gmail.com.

Abstract: Copper Oxides nanoparticles (CuONPs) were synthesized using a microwave technique of aqueous leaf extract of *Euphorbia helioscopia* L. EhCuONPs were tailored to different concentrations of copper Acetate in aqueous and organic Solvents of *Euphorbia helioscopia* L. leaf extract with stoichiometry proportion. The synthesis of nanoparticles is applicable, as natural resources for the better the environment because it helps reduced the use of hazardous toxic chemicals. Using XRD the crystalline existence of EhCuONPs has been established, confirming the formation of copper metal oxides. UV-Vis spectra of EhCuONPs confirmed the reduction of Cu^{3+} to Cu^{2+} . The FTIR spectra indicate the existence of functional groups of flavonoids and terpenoids intermixing with copper metal having Cu-O interacting peaks, which are responsible for nanoparticle reduction and progression. FTIR spectral study suggested that the flavonoids, terpenoids and phenols molecules can applicable to stabilization of EhCuONPs nanoparticles. SEM Image study the morphology of EhCuONPs nanoparticles were globular-spherical with an average size of 26-88 nm. *Euphorbia* Medicinal Plants have been used by traditional people resources as a drug and remedy for various diseases. This study was planned to account to the antimicrobial and antifungal activity of copper-oxide metal and Phytochemical of *Euphorbia helioscopia* and EhCuONPs nanoparticles.

Keywords: Euphorbiaceae, EhCuONPs, antimicrobial, traditional, and nanoparticles.

Introduction: Nanomaterials have tremendous applicability trends in the research era, due to their high potential to revolutionize a various application, having more curious and future scope challenges in microbial or pest management. The few decays ago, nano-materials synthesis approach have been improved using plant extract as sources of reducing and stabilizing agents to produce metal and metal oxide nanoparticles (NPs) for medicinal and biological applicability [1]. The 'green revolution in fabrication' of NPs and nano-composites has been reported as applicable as compared with rutting way like chemical and physical Synthetic methods, since greenway synthesis terms is usually cheap, safe, quick, and does not require high pressure, energy, and temperature nor the use of extremely toxic chemicals for environmental dangerous [2]. The Green-synthesized of Nanoparticle methodology have usually done in an aqueous suspension solution of reduction of metal ions by plant extract composition soluble in water, therefore the final product is an ideal formulation to treat with antimicrobial and antifungal study [3]. Metal oxides NPs having plant extract play a major role in pharmaceutical, industrial, and biotechnological applications. Copper and copper-based nanostructure materials have efficient toxicity as applicable properties which are generally used in catalysis, antimicrobial, antifungal, pest control, and several health-related applications. The Common name of the *Euphorbia* plant is Madwoman's Milk, the *Euphorbia helioscopia* L belongs to the family of Euphorbiaceae and is a local medicinal herb used by ethnos practitioners, as well as Unani medicine. The *Euphorbia* plants sap contains latex which is toxic on ingestion and highly irritant externally, causing photosensitive skin reactions and severe inflammation, especially on contact with eyes or open cuts. The toxicity can remain high even in dried plant material also; the sap of this plant is

carcinogenic in nature [4-5]. In reported works, it has been treated in various applications such as wound healing, as an anti-coagulant, and anti-fungal agent, and in the treatment of various infectious skin diseases, it has anticancer properties. The seeds of this plant, mixed with roasted pepper, have been used in the treatment of cholera. The milky sap is applied externally to skin eruptions [6-7]. Cu nanoparticles have the more interested of many scientists due to their potential properties in wound dressings and biocides properties, it has been widely studied due to their antimicrobial and antifungal activity against a wide range of pathogens and insect pests [8].

In the present study, EhCuONPs nanoparticle synthesized by green synthesis method by using *Euphorbia helioscopia* L. plants was investigated for the synthesis of CuO Nanoparticles by ultrasonication methodology, the synthesized Product confirmed CuO metal oxides of the nanomaterial formation by XRD, SEM, U.V. and FTIR spectroscopy technique. The EhCuONPs nanoparticle materials study their toxicity applicability by antibacterial and antifungal activity in the given work.

2 Methodology:

1. Collection of *Euphorbia helioscopia* leaves: The fresh leaves of *Euphorbia helioscopia* were collected from rural areas of Mana village, Taluka-murtizapur Dist-Akola. The *Euphorbia helioscopia* leaves were washed with tap water, shade-dried at room temperature, and powdered by an Mixer and Grandier.

2. Sohellate extraction and steam distillation method this method, 20 gm *Euphorbia helioscopia* leaves powder dissolved in 300ml solvent in water and Chloroform, continues heating for 3hr. After the process is carried out get leaves extracted. All leaf extract is filtered.

3. Filtration- Filtration was done to separate the components of a mixture of a liquid and an insoluble plant material.

4. Synthesized EhCuONPs nanoparticles: In this method near about 30-40 ml *Euphorbia helioscopia* leaf extract was taken in a 100 mL Pyrex beaker and heated at 60°C and 2gms of copper acetate monohydrate stirrer and mixed with extract for 1hour with speed of 400 rpm for stirrer. Then, the mixture was kept in ultrasonication for half an hour at 500 w at 80°C heating the mixture in a 100 mL Pyrex beaker, after the process the metal is totally mixed in the sample. Then transfer the mixture to a porcelain crucible, and dried in the furnace at 300°C for 2 hours. After heating, the material was powdered. Then powder was centrifuged three times with deionized water at 2000 rpm for 10 min and the supernatant was discarded. The powder of the sample was used for characterizing EhCuONPs nanoparticles. Purified EhCuONPs were dried overnight and were used for further characterization and catalytic application.

5. TLC Chromatography: TLC is used to help determine and separate the number of pure components in a mixture, the identity of compounds, and the purity of a chemical constitutions. We used TLC 3.5cm and added the *Euphorbia helioscopia* leaf extract drop and EhCuONPs drop

then the TLC plate. Compose the mixture of purified water and acetone as a mobile phase. As the solvent system on the chromatogram was applied the Euphorbia helioscopia leaf extract solution was applied to the standard mixture Transfer to the solvent system and rest out, this spot is formed, then the TLC plate is transferred to the U.V.-cabinet and mark the spot, and calculate the Rf value, after calculating the Rf value, the Rf value of EhCuONPs was 0.48 is observed and the Rf value of is 0.62, for Euphorbia helioscopia leaf extract of plant.

3 Results and Discussion: The Synthesized EhCuONPs nanoparticle material formation is confirmed by various spectroscopy catheterization techniques.

3.1 UV-Vis spectral analysis: The formation of Copper oxide nanoparticles was monitored by UV-Vis. Spectroscopy model Shimadzu UV-2401. UV-visible spectroscopy is an important and reliable research tool for the structural characterization of metallic nanoparticles. UV-Vis spectroscopy provides information about nanoparticle structure, size, stability, concentration, and aggregation. Synthesized EhCuONPs nanoparticle was confirmed by reported works the absorption peaks at the wavelength near to 588 nm. The absorption peak is observe due to the surface Plasmon resonance property of the nanoparticle, which occurs due to the oscillations of free electrons on the surface of the nanoparticle and interaction with wavelength of irradiated light [9] (Fig. 3.1). This blue shift observe a reduction in the diameter of the CuO nanoparticle [10]. The U.V.Visible spectra CuO typically show broad primary absorption peaks at often around 280nm to 320nm region and weaker absorption peaks at 560nm to 580 nm region. These peaks indicate inter-band transition and surface plasma resonance. The crystalline structure of CuO nanoparticles affects the absorption spectrum [11]. The concentration of Euphorbia plant extract changes it also change different organic reducing agents. The stoichiometry proportion of plants extract and at higher concentrations, the biomolecules act as reducing agents and cap the nanoparticle surfaces protecting them from aggregation [12]. The U.V. Visible Spectra of Synthesized EhCuONPs nanoparticles indicate the broad peak at 280-320 nm for the formation of EhCuONPs due to bimolecular intermixing as reducing agent with copper oxides metals and secondary weak peaks at 580-610 nm. The second graph indicates pure Copper oxide particles that are metal oxides range that also Primary base peak of copper metal oxides at near 255 to 280 nm Metal to oxides charge transfer transition and η -JI, and tail at 550nm secondary peaks, both comparative metal oxides and EhCuONPs indicate the formation of nanoparticle.

Fig. 3.1 UV-Vis spectral analysis EhCuONPs nanoparticle

3.2 FTIR spectral analysis: The FTIR spectrum of the formation of EhCuONPs nanoparticle was monitored by the FTIR spectroscopy model Shimadzu FTIR shown in fig 3.2. The Stretching between Cu–O bond is due to monoclinic CuO was responsible for the infrared bands at 603 cm^{-1} [12]. The CuO and M-O Stretching vibration are responsible for the other two peaks, which are located at 862 and 718 cm^{-1} . The stretching and bending vibration of hydroxyl groups adsorb on the surface of CuONPs may be the cause of the absorption peaks that arise at 1112 and 3432 cm^{-1} the confirm of CuO from the green synthesis method by the presence of significant infrared bands at about $400\text{-}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The CuO nanoparticle typically shows the related peaks of Cu-O bond stretching vibration commonly observed peaks at around $603\text{-}601\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $509\text{-}493\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $481\text{-}413\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [13]. Typically a broad band around $3400\text{-}3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can indicate the presence of O-H Stretching due to flavonoid or terpenoids adsorbed at the high surface area of nanoparticle. The peaks related to C-H stretching or bending vibration at 2942 cm^{-1} from the capping agent used during the synthesized

Fig 3.2 FTIR spectrum of EhCuONPs nanoparticle

3.3. XRD spectral analysis : The XRD spectrum is shown in Fig 3.3. EhCuONPs nanoparticles obtained at drying at 500°C and XRD pattern of CuO-NPs at 300°C temperature the peak compared with the standard data matched with a monoclinic phase of CuO Nanoparticles and consistent with JCPDS data. The crystalline size is calculated using Debye Scherrer equation [14]

$$D = 0.9\lambda / \beta \cos\theta$$

Where λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the line broadening at half the maximum intensity in radians, θ is the Bragg angle.

Sr.No Intense peaks	2 θ Theata	FWHM(β)	Average Size of EuCuONPs nm
1	16.56	3.272	27.28332nm
2	19.25	0.223	
3	25.81	0.43	
4	27.29	4.277	
5	27.78	5.41	
6	35.59	1.23	
7	40.16	2.83	

Fig 3. 3. XRD spectrum of EhCuONPs nanoparticle

Table3.3.1. Average Size of EuCuONPs Particle in nm

From the calculations, the average crystalline size of the synthesized EhCuONPs nanoparticle is 27.2833 nm. The xrd peaks match with reported peak that confirm that our synthesized EhCuONPs is monoclines crystalline in nature.

3.4. SEM surface Morphology analysis:- SEM is a powerful tool used to visualize the surface morphology of materials. It provides detailed images of the surface structure, including features like roughness, texture, and shape. The globular and rectangular size of the sample of EhCuONPs that can be imaged by SEM. The SEM image confirms that the material of EhCuONPs is by using reducing plants extract of Euphorbia helioscopia is useful to the formation and confirmation of nanomaterial having globular morphology as like cauliflower. The SEM morphology observed and count the Size of CuO particles found to be 28-88nm region

Fig 3.4. SEM surface Morphology

3.5. Biomedical Applications:

3.5.1. Antibacterial activity: The Covid-19 era is more teach to human personal as well as new leading scientist that nano-based nano-based therapies have been used to diagnose and treat diseases to from the new drugs . At the time of new drug discovery the antibacterial activities of nanoparticles have been tested against different pathogenic bacterial strains. The literature serve reported those copper oxides based nanoparticles are highly toxic in nature to pathogen bacteria. The biofabricated nanoparticles of CuO have wide applicability due t their uniform morphology , more surface area , bio compatible nature to tested agents bacterial pathogens . The synthesized copperoxides particles have vigorous antimicrobial activity against bacterial strains [15].

The green synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles using leaf extract and evaluated their antibacterial activities against urinary tract infection (UTI) causing pathogens [15]. The highest zone was observed against Escherichia coli with an average diameter of 19 mm at a concentration of 25 ug/ml [15]. The authors tested that the green synthesized euphorbia plant extract copper oxide nanoparticles exhibited potential activities against S.aureu and Escherichia coli.

The results reported that the green synthesized copper oxide nanoparticles exhibited intense bacterial activities against, Staphylococcus aureus and Escherichia coli at 50mg/ml. The EhCuONPs were compared with Copper acetate solution and standard antibiotic ampicillin at a concentration of 20mg/ml-80mg/ml in table 4. 1. The EhCuONPs exhibited more activity than Copper acetate solution and standard antibiotic solution. The EhCuONPs were fairly toxic to Bacillus sp., E. coli and Staphylococcus aureus with the inhibition zone of 24, and 26 mm.. Some of the contributions are shown in Table 4. Antibacterial activities of fabricated copper oxide nanoparticles .The synthesized nanoparticles' characterization was confirmed by UV-Vis, FT-IR, and XRD, techniques and investigated antimycotic activity.

Table 3.5. 1. Antibacterial activities of Eh copper oxide nanoparticles determined

Organism	Concentration (mg)	Zone Inhibition		
		Control	Standard	Sample
Staphylococcus aureus	50mg	nil	24	26nm
Escherichia coli.	50mg	Nil	22	24nm

Table 3.5. 2. Antibacterial activities of EhCuONPs at different concentration

Organism	Zone Inhibition at different concentration			
	20mg	40mg	60mg	80mg
Staphylococcus aureus	12	14	15	17
Escherichia coli.	13	17	21	25

Fig 3.5. 1 Graphical presentation Antimicrobial study EhCuONps at different concentration

Fig 3.5.2. Antimicrobial study of EhCuONps

The metal-Oxides nanoparticles interact with bacterial cell membrane, at that time cell membrane of bacterial cell wall growth inhibited and disturbs the cell wall membrane cause lead to death due to liberated reactive oxygen species of metal oxides. The Euphorbia plant is toxicity and copper oxides have powerful toxic contamination to liberate oxygen and superoxide's cause the DNA and protein to prevent biofilm production, mechanism is shown in Figure 3:4:1.

3.5.2 Antifungal activity: The fungal disease has become a more serious health problem, especially in patients having a weak immune system such as AIDS or cancer patients undergoing chemical treatment [19]. The antifungal activity of copper oxide nanoparticles has been investigated for biomedical applications [20]. The antifungal activities of copper oxide nanoparticles have been less studied as compared to antibacterial activity. The synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles using the fungal strain has been reported. The authors tested these green synthesized nanoparticles against pathogenic fungal strains such as *Candida albicans*. They further concluded that the green fabricated copper oxide nanoparticles showed healthy activities against *Candida albicans* as reported in table 3.5.4. .

3.5.4. **Antifungal** activities of EhCuONPs determined by agar well diffusion.

Organism	Concentration (mg)	Zone Inhibition		
		Control	Standard	Sample
<i>Candida albicans</i>	50mg	nil	20	24 nm

Table 3.5. 5. **Antifungal** activities of EhCuONPs at different concentration

Organism	Zone Inhibition at different concentration			
	20mg	40mg	60mg	80mg
<i>Candida albicans</i>	15	18	21	24

Fig 3.5. 3 Graphical presentation Antimicrobial study EhCuONps at different concentration

Fig 3.5.4. Antimicrobial study of EhCuONps

4. Conclusion: To synthesis of metal oxides nanoparticles by using biological natural sources such as plant extract is tremendous attractive field because their diverse applications. This new research era is better applicability to nano-medicinal science such as antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anticancer, antioxidant, drug delivery, and many more. The Copper oxide nanoparticles have been synthesized through different way such as chemical, physical, and biological approaches. The physical and chemical way are expensive and use toxic chemicals that may cause a hazardous effect to environmental issue again more cost for producing the nanoparticles. As compared to all approaches, the biological approach is environment-friendly, low cost-effective, reliable, stable, low energy consumption, and a straightforward method.

In this study, we have summarized the fabrication of copper oxide nanoparticles using Euphorbia plant extract as biological sources, to synthesis of copper oxides nanoparticles their interactive mechanisms confirm by FTIR and UV-Visible spectroscopy to observe the metal oxides formation and biological contain like flavonoid, terpenoids as reducing and binding agents to metal oxides formation. The XRD characterizations data confirm the Copper oxides binding and structure of metal oxides as well as size of nanoparticles formation by using Bragg's and Debye Scherrer equation to nano size particles is formation. SEM monograph observed surface, morphology and size of copper oxides nanoparticles confirmation EhCuONps. The diverse biomedical applications like antimicrobial species and antifungal activity is applicable to infection of pathogen to human beings. The future scope of this study to upgrade the biomedical applications to anticancer activity of EhCuONPs, more research work should focus on possible methods of minimizing CuO-NPs' toxicity while maintaining and improving their biological efficiency. In covid 19-the major important challenge to protect human health's from the pathogenous bacteria, fungi and virus also.

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